

Practice Abstract no. 37

Industry & food system actors' views on opportunities linked to open data sharing

The #Data4Food Cluster comprising the [DRG4Food](#), [FOODITY](#), [FoodDataQuest](#), and [SOSFood](#) projects organised a joint workshop in June 2025 to discuss challenges, enablers, and gains related to data sharing and AI-driven solutions for sustainable food systems. Two breakout room sessions explored perspectives from both consumers/citizens and industry/food system actors on data sharing and AI in food systems.

This practice abstract discusses industry & food system actors' views on the main opportunities linked to open data sharing.

- **Research and innovation advancements**, which opens the door for faster, more impactful scientific and research advancements (boosting EU competitiveness) and supports the development of data-driven AI solutions and applications.
- **Digital advancements**, including new or improved solutions for quantifying and measuring food products throughout the processing value chain could better evaluate the environmental, social, and health impacts of food production.
- **Supply chain optimisation**, including opportunities for better production planning and increased supply chain agility, and real-time supply and demand balance, leading to a more seamlessly coordinated supply chain.
- **Consumer empowerment and transparency**, which facilitates more informed consumer choices (e.g., food source, composition) as well as the potential for new and better solutions offering personalized advice on food intake, diets, and behaviors to promote sustainable eating.
- **Increased transparency and trust**, which has the potential to foster greater transparency and fairness. This would be achieved by enabling more scrutiny of processes and increasing accountability among all stakeholders.
- **Gaining a competitive advantage**, which is seen as the use of available data to compete with healthier, greener products providing a key advantage for the industry and EU food competitiveness, especially given increasing eco- and food-consciousness among consumers.

The aforementioned information is available and further detailed in the joint report developed by the #Data4Food Cluster "What Helps and What Hurts When Sharing Data for Sustainable Food Solutions."

(DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17860651>)

